

battery and carrying box, weighs 4.4 kg. It can be carried in any convenient small box. A plastic box (Photo 2) will permit the unit to float in the paddy water, although the position of the battery must be adjusted for proper balance. One operator can emasculate 12 panicles/hour with the unit, depending on the operator's skill and other variables.

The entire unit (including the box and a small battery charger) costs about US\$150. Prices may vary, depending on the local availability of the components. The pump, motor, filter, and trap are manufactured by Gast Manufacturing Corp., Benton Harbor, Michigan, US. Units may be purchased at cost through the Plant Breeding Department, IRRI. □

2. Portable vacuum emasculator in a plastic carrying case that allows the unit to float when operated in the field.

Scientific publication among rice breeders in Asia

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The scientific papers or articles that 38 rice breeders had published or had accepted for publication in 1974-75 were analyzed as part of a research project on rice breeding programs in 10 Asian nations: Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, Iran, Korea, Nepal, Pakistan, Philippines, Sri Lanka, and Thailand.

The 38 scientists had authored or coauthored 183 scientific papers during the 2 years — an average of 2.4 papers/scientist per year. Fifty-three percent of the papers were published in journals within the scientist's own nation; 23% in institutional publications; 18% in journals in highly developed nations; and 6% in international publications such as the International Rice Commission Newsletter or the SABRAO Newsletter.

The distribution of publication productivity was later determined and compared with that predicted by Derek de Solla Price, who states that *half of the publications produced by a population of n scientists are authored by the most productive of about \sqrt{n} of the population*. The inverse-square root law has held true since the early scientific journals of the 17th century, but most of the research has been conducted on

chemists and physicists in the western nations.

Half of the publications were authored by only 6 of the breeders — roughly the square root of the sample of 38 breeders. And 50% of the breeders authored 11% of the total publications (see figure).

That suggests that the scientific norms of rice breeders are similar to those of other scientists, and that Asian scientists'

norms are similar to those of peer scientists in America and Europe.

When social characteristics of the scientists were compared, it was found that all the high publishers and 30% of the low publishers held the Ph.D. On the average, the high publishers were about 3 years older than the low publishers and had about 3 more years of professional experience working with rice (see table).

A study of Asian rice breeders and the scientific publications that they authored or coauthored over a 2-year period (1974-75) showed that 50% of the scientists had written or helped write 11% of the total scientific articles published by the sample; 16% had published 50% of the articles. One hundred and eighty-three scientific articles and contributions to scientific books published by 38 rice breeders at 27 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 10 Asian nations.

A comparison of the educational and sociological backgrounds of 19 low-publishing and 6 high-publishing rice breeders in Asia. Taken from a sample of 38 rice breeders at 27 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 10 Asian nations, 1975.

Characteristic	Rice breeders	
	Low publishers (19)	High publishers (6)
Highest educational attainment		
B.S. (70)	35	0
M.S. (%)	35	0
Ph.D. (%)	30	100
Source of highest degree		
Local (%)	70	33
Other Asian countries (76)	5	17
Highly developed country (70)	25 ^a	50
Av. age (yr)	40.5	43.8
Av. professional experience (yr)	12.2	15.5
Travel ^b		
Foreign travel (70)	79	83
Trips (av. no./scientist)	2.3	1.5
Preferences for scientific publication ^c		
National (%)	42	17
International (76)	10	0
Highly developed country (76)	32	83
No response (%)	16	0

^a Of six low-publishing Ph.D.'s, four were educated in highly developed nations. One scientist whose highest educational attainment was an M.S. degree had received the degree in a highly developed nation.

^b Scientists who had traveled abroad in the past 5 years.

^c When asked to name the scientific journal or publication in which they would most like to publish an article about their research results, if they could be assured of publication anywhere in the world.

They averaged slightly fewer trips abroad.

The purpose of the research was to better understand how scientific information moves among Asian rice improvement programs. The author in no way implies that the rice breeders who

published the most papers, or even papers in the most prestigious journals, are better or worse scientists than the others.

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Cult. 3885, Cult. 3948. Cult. 3965, Cult. 3964, Cult. 3868, Cult. 5996, Cult. 4295, Cult. 4078, Cult. 3904, Cult. 3900, Cult. 6001, and Cult. 3872.

The moderately resistant rices were: Cult. 3953, Cult. 3916, Cult. 3961, Cult. 3886, Cult. 5994, Cult. 6003, Cult. 3867, Cult. 6008, Cult. 3945, Cult. 3877, Cult. 3987, Cult. 4116, Cult. 13493, CR-1014, Jaya, Bala, IR5, CR-6, Cauvery, Bhavani, Pankaj, Jarnuna, IET-1991, CO2, C07, COI9, C022, GEB24, C027, C028, C023, C031, C032, C036, ADT13, ADT25, ASD4, ASD9, ASD13, ASD7, PTBI5, Tetep, Zenith, Dawn, 46-Palman, IR3273, IR1103-15-8-3, IR1614-389-3, IR579-126, IET2913, V-11/3, V-238, Cult. 2226, Cult. 1900, AC82, Thangasamba, T-336, MTU-5715, F13-22, V12, V121, T215, T1157, T347, Mottai Karu, AC-2959, Jagannath, and Malagkit Sungsong. □

Rice ragged stunt disease in India

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Ragged stunt, a new virus disease of rice, was observed at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore, India, in February 1978.

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Varietal resistance of rice to sheath blight

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Rice varieties and cultures in Tamil Nadu were screened for resistance to sheath blight disease of rice caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*. During the maximum-tillering stage, 1,404 cultivars were

inoculated with the *R. solani* pathogen by the straw bit method. Thirty-six rices were resistant and 68 moderately resistant.

The resistant rices were: ADT 22, ADT 5, CO20, Ponni, Ratna, Thillainayagam (S.AR) Cult. 55-100, V228, W449, Wase Aikoku, T1185, V42, Dular, Cult. 2100, Cult. 6547, Cult. 2210-2, Cult. 5143, Kam Ban Ngan, IR1544-340, DGWG, IR1156-501-P, Cult. 3879, Cult. 3896, Cult. 3875,

Percentage of hills infected by ragged stunt virus disease. Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Infected hills ^a (%)
Cult. 644	89
IR30	83
Cult. 1722	83
Cult. 5202	14
IR28	73
Cult. 2361	13
Cult. 2684	69
Cauvery	64
IET2222	63
Cult. 13613	62
Cult. 658	52
IET1444	44
Cult. 1893	43
Vaigai	42
IR36	35

^aMean of 4 replications.